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ANNOTATION

This study examines the relationship between the dynamics of neurological retardation and developmental delays in premature and low birth-weight infants during the first six months of life. The infants were observed dynamically, and their neuropsychological development was assessed using standardized developmental scales. Clinical-functional research included the evaluation of neurological sensitivity, muscle tone, conditioned responses, and reflexes. Additionally, ultrasound examinations of the brain were conducted. Recognizing the importance of neonatal reflexes in diagnosing nervous system injuries, we investigated the occurrence and persistence of these reflexes in the monitored infants. Notably, low-birth-weight newborns exhibited spasms in their arms and legs

Keywords: neurological retardation, infants, children, reflexes, development

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**O'RTACHA VA OG'IR DARAJALI ASFIKSIYA BILAN TUG'ILGAN
CHAQALOQLARDA ASAB-RUXIY RIVOJLANISHNING KECHIKISHI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Muddatiga etib va muddatidan avval tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar hayotining birinchi 6 oy ichida asab ruxiy rivojlanishining orqada qolishi dinamikasini bir birlariga bog'liqligini o'rganish.

Klinik-funksional tadqiqotda nevrologik (sezgirligi, mushak tonusi, shartsiz va pay reflekslarni), bosh miyani ultratovush tekshiruvini o'tkazildi.

Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar reflekslarini aniqlash, asab tizimidagi shikastlanishlarni topik tashxislashda katta yordam berishini hisobga olib, biz ushbu reflekslarni kuzatilayotgan bolalarda paydo bo'lishi va saqlanishini dinamikada o'rgandik.

Kam vaznli yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar qo'l-oyoq mushaklarida asimmetrik gipertonuslar aniqlanadi.

Kalit sozlar: chaqaloqlar, asab ruxiy, reflekslari, qo'l-oyoqlar, mushaklar gipertonuslar

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ЗАДЕРЖКА НЕРВНО-ПСИХИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ (НПР) У НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ ДЕТЕЙ, РОДИВШИХСЯ СО СРЕДНЕЙ И ТЯЖЕЛОЙ СТЕПЕНЬЮ АСФИКСИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Изучить взаимосвязь задержки нервно-психического развитие (НПР) доношенных и недоношенных новорожденных в динамике первых шести месяцев жизни.

Проведено клинико-функциональное исследование - неврологическая чувствительность, мышечный тонус, безусловные и сухожильные рефлексы, УЗИ исследование головного мозга. У новорожденных с малой массой тела появляются признаки спастичности в верхних и нижних конечностях. Выявляется асимметрично гипертонус мышцы верхних и нижних конечностей.

Ключевые слова: нервно-психически развитие, новорожденные, рефлексы, конечности, гипертонус мышц.

Adabiyotlar ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, asab-ruxiy rivojlanishining kechikishi (ARK) ko'pincha muddatidan avval tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda topiladi va bu erta tug'ilgan bolalar asab tizimining xali to'la etilmaganligi bilan bog'liqdir [1, 2, 3, 6]. Biroq, asab tizimining etuklik darajasi har doim ham etuk tug'ilganlik darajasiga mos kelavermaydi [4, 7]. Shu munosabat bilan, muddatida tug'lgan bolalarga nisbatan muddatidan avval tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning klinik- nevrologik tizimi dinamikasini diqqat bilan to'liq tekshiruv o'tkazilishi kerak.

Pediatric va Neonatologiyada markaziy asab tizimi va orqa miya shikastlanishlar tashxisini shartsiz reflekslarni o'rganish orqali qo'yiladi [2, 8]. Bunda, orqa miya shikastlari tashxisida shartsiz reflekslarning qo'llanishi ma'lum bir ilmiy nuqtai jihatdan muayyan qiziqish uyg'otadi [1,2,9].

Shunday qilib, serebral shikastlanishlarida oral segmental avtomatizm (Babkin, Kussmaul, va emish) reflexlari ko'pincha "zaiflanishi" kuzatilsa [1,2,10], orqa miya shikastlanishlarida esa - umurtqa motor avtomatizm reflekslaridan: tservikal shikastlarida (ushlab olish, Робинсон, Мороз, ximoya) reflekslari pasayadi [3,4,8,9], ko'krak va bel mintaqasining shikastlanishi bilan-qo'llab-quvvatlash reflekslari (itarishi), avtomatik yurish, emaklash (pereza, Galant, Bauer, Babinskiy) refleksilari ekstensorlarning o'zaro kesish joyida bu reflekslar tortilishi kuzatiladi [5,10].

Muddatida va muddatidan avval tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda shartsiz reflekslarni o'rganish markaziy asab tizimi va umurtqa tuzimlar kasalliklari aniq diagnostikasida amaliy ahamiyatga egadir [2,10].

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Muddatiga etib va muddatidan avval tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarni hayotining birinchi 6 oy ichida asab ruxiy rivojlanishini orqada qolishi dinamikasini bir birlariga bog'liqligini aniqlash.

Tadqiqot materiali va usullari. Hayotining dastlabki olti oyi davomida 40 ta muddatiga etib tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar (38-40 haftalik gestatsiya muddati) va 24 ta muddatidan avval tug'ilgan (32-37 haftalik gestatsiya muddati) bolalar dinamikada kuzatildi. Bu bolalarni asab ruxiy rivojlanishini, L.T.Jurba va E.M. Mostyukova shkalasi bo'yicha baholandi [5]. Klinik-funksional tadqiqot o'tkazildi: nevrologik (sezgirliги, mushak tonusi, shartsiz va pay reflekslarni), bosh miyani ultratovush tekshiruvu o'tkazildi (Pilips. - 480).

Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar reflekslarini aniqlash asab tizimidagi shikastlanishlarni topik tashxislashda katta yordam berishini hisobga olib, biz ushbu reflekslarning kuzatilayotgan bolalarda paydo bo'lishi va saqlanishini dinamikada o'rgandik.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Klinik tadqiqotlarda tug'ilish vazni past bo'lgan 27 (25,0%, $p < 0.01$) chaqaloqlarning oyoq va qo'llarida spastik belgilar borligini qayd etdilar. Ushbu bolalarda o'ziga xos holatlar aniqlandi: qo'llar tirsak bo'g'imida qattiq bukilgan - tirsak bo'g'imidagi burchak $< 45^\circ$ bo'lgan, elka va bilak tanaga qattiq yopishgan (Shali sinamasi), qo'llar musht bo'lib siqilgan, qo'llarini tortsa boshini tashash bosqichi ko'rilmaydi (Robinson refleksi), qorin bo'shlig'ini to'xtatib turish paytida tanasi gorizontol holatga kelishi, itarish refleksi paytida son-tos va tizza bo'g'imlar burchaklarining kichrayishi, oyoqlar chalishtirish ekstensor refleksida bukilish fazasi cheklangan (oyoq adduksiyasi), ($< 90^\circ$) burchakdan kichikroq, oyoqlarni ochilishida (har bir tomonda 45° dan), tizza bo'g'imlaridagi katta burchak ($> 120^\circ$) - "oyoq uchida yurish" simptomi yuzaga keladi.

Bizlar yuqoridagi ko'rsatilgan metodik usullar natijalariga ko'ra qo'l va oyoqlar mushaklarining gipertonus assimetriyasini aniqladik. Bunday bolalarning pozasi "qilichboz" pozasiga o'xshardi (qo'l va oyoqlar bir tomonda ochiq, boshqa tomonida esa yopiq), bu bizga - 7 ta bolada chap tomanlama va - 11 bolalarda esa o'ng tomonlama spastik gemiparezni borligini o'rnatishga asos bo'ldi. Shunga ko'ra, bolalar oyoqlaridagi spastik parezlarni interpretatsiyasida mos ravishda, 1 (1,25%) va 8 tasida (8,33% $p < 0,01$) kuzatildi. Bunday bolalar qo'llarida keskin giperflrksiya, oyoqlarida esa ekstensor gipertonus xisobiga «bokschi» ko'rinishi aniqlandi.

Shu bilan birga, tirsak bo'g'imining burchagi $< 45^\circ$ bo'lib, lin.axillaris posteriorda tirsakni ushlab qolishi, Shali sinomasida boshning oldiga burilishi (teskari bo'lish o'rnidaga) refleks Robinsonday, gorizontol holatda ensa mushaklarining tortilishi (qorin bo'shlig'ini osiltirishi) va itarish refleksida oyoqlarning atetoz xarakati, ekstenzorlarni kesishish refleksi, oyoqlarni yon tomonga burishi kuzatildi.

Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda bu belgilar spastik tetraparezni namoyon bo'lishi sifatida qaraladi.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, qo'l va oyoqlar mushaklarining gipertonisi sinamasi (katlama pichog'i sinamasi) solishtirganda spastik hemiparez (18 holat) va tetraparez (9 holat) bir hil emas edi.

Shunday qilib, 11 holatda (61,1%) spastik hemiparez va 8 holatda (88,9%) tetraparez namoyon bo'lgan. Ushbu bolalar qo'llaridagi fleksor mushaklarining gipertonisi sinamasi, oyoqlar mushaklariga nisbatan ustunlik qiladi. Ularning qo'llarini tortganda yuqori qarshilik (gipertonus) borligi aniqlanadi, Robinson sinamasi paytida boshni orqaga tashlash bosqichi cheklangan bo'ladi, Shali sinamasi paytida elka va tirsak bo'g'imlarining harakatlarida katta cheklovlar mavjud bolib, va Landau refleksi paytida boshning ekstensiyasi kuzatiladi.

Ushbu guruhdagi bolalarning 78,9% da tortish refleksi va 78,7% da ekstensorlarning o'zaro kesishish refleksi saqlanib qolganligi kuzatildi. Spastik hemi va tetraparezli chaqaloqlarni klinik tekshiruvdan o'tkazganda, biz ularning "bachadon bo'yni" deb ataladigan umurtqa pog'onasi simptom komplekslari bilan kombinatsiyasiga e'tibor qaratdik.

Shunday qilib, hemiparez (38,9%) va 1 ta tetraparez (11,1%) bo'lgan 7 bolada biz bachadon bo'yni (tservikal) simptomlarining ba'zi konsentratsiyasini qayd etdik: qiyshiq bo'yin (75%), gormoshka simptomlari (87,5%), "tushayotgan" bosh (100,0%), qo'g'irchoq boshi (50,0%). Ushbu alomatlar ko'pincha Klod-Bernard-Horner sindromi (87,5%) va Kofferat sindromlari (75%) bilan birgalashib kelishlari mumkin.

Shu munosabat bilan J. Ratnerning miyadagi tserebral spastik parezi bosh miyadagi vosita yo'llaridan (oldingi markaziy egriliklar, miya oyoqchalari, varoliev ko'prigi va uzunchoq miya) shikastlanishi bilan ham, "qalam" turidagi umurtqa pog'onasining (uzunligi bo'ylab) lateral ustunlar (piramida yo'llari) shikastlanishi natijasida ham yuzaga kelishi mumkinligi haqidagi bayonotini keltirib o'tish kerak.

Spastikligini tashdiqlash uchun (markaziy yoki periferikligini), shuningdek ularning kelib chiqish genezisini (serebral, o'murtqa - yuqori servikal) tasdiqlash uchun jadvalda keltirilgan bir qator shartsiz reflekslarni o'rganish muhim yordam beradi.

Jadvaldagi ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, miya va umurtqa pog'onasi spastik hemi va tetraparez namoyon bo'lgan yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda oral avtomatizmi guruhidan (emish, xobotko, qidiruv, kaft-og'iz) shartsiz reflekslar yo'qolish chastotasida statistik farq qilmaydi ($p > 0.05$), ikkala guruhda ham bu reflekslarni chaqirish chastotasi sezilarli darajada kamayadi. Buning sababi shundaki, barcha reflekslar miya asosi darajasida yopiladi (varoliev ko'prigi, uzunchoq miya) va revlektor efferent yo'llaridagi reflekslar quyidagi V, VII, IX, X va XII juftliklaridir (Barashnev Yu.I., 2001).

Tserebral va orqa miya (yuqori bo'yin) spastik parezlarining topik tashxisida suprasegmental posotonik avtomatizm guruhi reflekslaridan - assimetrik va nosimmetrik serviko-tonik reflekslari (NSTR, SSTR) va tonik labirint refleksi (TLR) - juda ma'lumotli bo'lib chiqdi. ASTR ($p < 0.001$), SSTR ($p < 0.008$), TLR ($p < 0.004$), umurtqa genizli hemi va tetraparez namoyon bo'lgan yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda sezilarli darajada tez-tez (75% dan 87.5%) gacha, markaziy genezning spastik parez klinikasi bo'lgan yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda bu reflekslarning yo'qolish chastotasi ahamiyatsiz (26,3 dan 36,8%) bo'ldi. Gemiparezli kasal bolalarda bu reflekslar assimetrik ravishda chiqib ketdi.

Jadval

Spastik parezlarning namoyon bo'lishi bilan yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda shartsiz reflekslarni xarakteristikasi (zaiflashadimi) (%)

№	Shartsiz reflekslar	Markazdan kelib chiqqan gemi- va tetra parezlar		Orqa miyadan kelib chiqqan gemi- va tetra parezlar		Up	P
		n=19		n=8			
		abs	%	abs	%		
I. Oral avtomatizm reflekslari (OAR)							
1	Emish refleksi zaiflashgan	15	78,9	7	87,5	0,55	H.d.*
2	Proboscis, qiyinchiliksiz, zaiflashgan	17	89,5	6	75,0	0,92	H.d.
3	Qidiruv, Kussmaul) chaqirilmaydi, zaiflashgan	15	78,9	6	75,0	0,22	H.d.
4	Kaft oral refleksi (Babkina), chaqirilmaydi, zaiflashadi	16	84,2	5	62,5	1,19	H.d.
II. Posotonik avtomatizmning suprasegmental reflekslari (PSR)							
5	Asimmetrik bo'yin-tonik refleksi (ABTR)	5	26,3	7	87,5	3,18	<0,001
6	Nosimmetrik bo'yin-tonik refleksi (NBTR)	5	26,3	7	75,0	2,41	<0,008
7	Tonik labirint refleksi (tlr)	7	36,8	7	87,5	2,64	<0,004
III. Orqa miya motor avtomatizmining reflekslari (OAR)							
8	Himoya	17	89,5	2	25,0	3,41	<0,001
9	Moro Refleksi	2	10,5	1	12,5	0,13	H.d.
10	Ushlash (Robinsona) kuchaytirish	5	26,3	5	62,5	1,77	<0,038
11	Galanta	3	15,8	2	25,0	0,54	H.d.

12	Pereza	4	21,1	3	37,5	0,86	Н.д.
13	Emaklash (Bauer)	3	15,8	2		0,54	Н.д.
14	Tayanch va avtomatik yurish	5	26,3	3	37,5	0,57	Н.д.

Qaydlar" n.d. sizning <1.64 da statistik jihatdan ahamiyatsiz ($p>0.0'5$). Ikki tomonlama FMT mezon. Fisherni hisobga olgan holda.

Shunday qilib, TLR ga ko'ra, bola orqa holatida yotganda paralich bo'lgan tomonida ekstensor mushaklar tonusi oshmaydi va qorin holatida yotganda paretik bo'g'inning fleksor mushaklarining reaksiyasi zaiflashadi. CBTR chaqirishda bola boshini oldinga egganda, qo'l va oyoqlar to'liq bukilmaydi, bosh orqaga burilganda qo'l va oyoqlar bukilishi assimetrik xolatda bo'ladi.

ABTR chaqirishda, boshni gemiparezdan kontralateral ravishda aylantirganda, bolalar boshlarini orqaga tashlaydilar (spastik qiyshiq bo'yin), paretik tomonda oyoq-qo'llarning fleksiyasi cheklangan (ekstensor gipertonisi), boshni esa gomolateral burganda oyoq-qo'llar parezi ensa tomonga buriladi (sog'lom tomonda) zaiflashadi.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, segmentlar usti pozotonik reflekslarning reflektor yoyi orqa miyaning yuqorigi uchta bo'yin segmentlari satxida kesishadi.

Orqa miya motor avtomatizmining (OMA) shartsiz reflekslaridan himoya refleksi ancha ma'lumotli bo'lib xisoblanadi. Orqa miya yuqori bo'yin genezli parezlari bo'lgan bolalarga nisbatan tserebral genezli spastik parezlari bo'lgan bolalarda ko'pincha bo'lmaydi 25,0% 89,5% ($p<0,001$).

Refleksning mohiyati shundan iboratki, agar bola qorin bilan yotqizilsa, u darhol bo'g'ilib qolmasligi uchun boshini yon tomonga buradi.

Pediatriya va neonatologiyada markaziy asab tizimi va umurtqa pog'onasining shikastlanishi tashxisida, shartsiz reflekslar o'rqli tashxisni aniqlash imkoni bo'ladi. Shu bilan birga, miya shikastlanishlarini tashxislashda shartsiz reflekslarni qo'llash ilmiy nuqtai nazarda muayyan qiziqish uyg'otadi.

Markaziy asab tizimi va umurtqa tuzilmasi kasalliklarini dolzarb tashxislashda to'liq va muddatidan avval tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda shartsiz reflekslarni o'rganish amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi. Kam vaznli yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar qo'l- oyoqlarida spastik belgilarning borligini ko'rsatadi. Qo'l- oyoq mushaklarida asimetrik gipertonuslar aniqlandi.

REFERENCES | СНОЧКИ | IQTIBOSLAR:

1. Авраменко В. Ю., Дегтярева М. В. Оценка состояния новорожденных детей с использованием методики Вирджинии Аппар (Virginia Apgar) и ее модификаций //Pediatriya named after GN Speransky. – 2021. – №. 3.
2. Жабченко И. А., Коваленко Т. М., Лищенко И.С. Перинатальные последствия длительного стресса в период пандемии и пути их коррекции: обзор литературы //Reproductive Medicine. – 2021. – №. 3 (48). – С. 6-14
3. Клиническая характеристика детей с экстремально низкой массой тела при рождении / Б.Т. Чарипова, Г.Н. Чистякова, М.Н. Тарасова, И.И. Ремизова // Уральский медицинский журнал. – 2010.-№5.-С.147-151.
4. Морозова Е.А., Морозов Д.В. Родовая травма центральной нервной системы и её отдалённые последствия //Международная остеопатическая конференция: Остеопатические аспекты качества жизни населения.– 2019.– С. 134-139.
5. Файзуллаева Х. Б. и др. Коррекция комплексного лечения при метаболическом ацидозе у новорожденных с тяжелой асфиксией //Журнал гепато-гастроэнтерологических исследований. – 2022. – №. 5
6. Шабалов Н.П. Неонатология: учеб. Пособие: в 2 т. – 5-е изд., испр. и доп. – М.: МЕД прессинформ, 2019. - Том 1. – 736 с
7. Sh N. G. et al. The specifics of neurosanographic changes in the diagnosis of posthypoxic

- complications in children born in asphyxia //Colloquium-journal. – Голопристанский міськрайонний центр зайнятості, 2020.– №.19(71). – С. 6-7.
8. Fayzullaeva H. et al. Metabolic status as an indicator of post-hypoxic complications in newborns born in asphyxia //European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 2. – С. 2370 - 2374.
 9. Herin, P. Neonatal kidney, fluids and electrolytes / P. Herin, A. Aperia //Curr-Opin-Pediatr. 2004. Apr. 6 (2). P. 154–157.
 10. Koletzko B., Beyer J., Brands B. et al. Early influences of nutrition on postnatal growth. Gillmah V.W., Gluckman P.D., Rosenfeld R.G: Recent advantages in growth research: Nutritional Molecular and Endocrine Perspectives. Nestle Nutr Inst Workshop Ser 2013: 71: 11-27.
 11. Johnson C. T., Burd I., Raghunathan R., Northing-Encephalopathy in Southern China: A Case-Control Study. Am J Perinatol. 2021 Aug;38(S 01): e182-e186.
 12. F. J., Graham E. M. Perinatal inflammation/doi: 10.1055/s-0040–1708884.
 13. Lorain P., Bower A., Gottardi E., Dommergues M., J Perinatol. 2016 Jun;36(6):448–52. doi: 10.1038/Foix L’Helias L., Guellec I., Kayem G. Risk factors for jp.2015.221. hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy in cases of severe acidosis: A case-control study. Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand.
 14. Vellamgot A. P., Salameh K., Habboub L. H.M., 2022 Apr;101(4):471–478. doi: 10.1111/aogs.14326. Pattuvalappil R., Elkabir N. A., Siam Y. S., Khatib H.

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

10 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

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